

33 kg K ha⁻¹ and F₂: 100 kg N ha⁻¹, 26 kg P ha⁻¹, and 50 kg K-ha⁻¹. In 'UP' plots, the seeds of cv Pant Dhan 4 were drilled in 20 cm rows on 20 Jun 1992 and 3 Jul 1993, and in P plots 30-d-old seedlings were transplanted on 23 Jul 1992 and 7 Jul 1993 with a spacing of 20 × 15 cm. Phosphorus and potash were given basally and N was applied in three splits, 50% P and 25% UP as basal; 25% P and 50% UP at tillering; and 25% (P and UP) at panicle initiation.

Disease incidence was recorded on five stools selected at random from each plot according to IRRI's 1988 *Standard evaluation system for rice*. The number of shoots at harvest was 360 m⁻² (1992) and 390 m⁻² (1993) in UP plots compared with 280 m⁻² (1992) and 270 m⁻² (1993) in P plots. Incidence of brown spot caused by *Cochliobolus miyabeanus* (Ito and Kuribayashi) Drechsler ex Dastur anamorph *Drechslera oryzae* (Breda de Hann) Subra and Jain was severe in both seasons. Fertility levels had no significant effect on the severity of brown spot, while tillage significantly

Disease and grain yield (t ha⁻¹) in puddled (P) and unpuddled plots (UP) at two fertilizer levels. Pantnagar, India, 1992 and 1993.

Treatment	Brown spot disease (%) ^a		Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
	1992	1993	1992	1993
120 kg N + 17 kg P + 33 kg K ha ⁻¹ (P)	19.54 (26.21)	22.2 (28.1)	5.3	5.8
100 kg N + 26 kg P + 50 kg K ha ⁻¹ (P)	17.05 (24.73)	19.4 (26.13)	6.6	6.1
120 kg N + 17 kg P + 33 kg K ha ⁻¹ (UP)	30.05 (33.21)	52.7 (46.55)	4.8	4.9
100 kg N + 26 kg P + 50 kg K ha ⁻¹ (UP)	29.43 (32.43)	44.4 (41.78)	5.2	5.8
CD (5%) Tillage	4.33	0.86	0.4	1.7
Fertility	ns	ns	0.4	1.7
CV	18.48	26.5	10.0	5.0

^aFigures in parentheses are angular values.

influenced it. The disease index was significantly lower in P than in UP plots, and the difference more pronounced in 1993 (see table).

During kharif 1992, yield was significantly higher in both P and UP plots. The yield was also higher in P than in UP plots. In 1993, however, treatment effects were not significant. The severity of brown spot increased

significantly in UP plots, an effect attributable to their higher plant population. Another reason may be the poor water management in UP plots with nutritional imbalance in the soil that aggravates the disease. Caution must be exercised in recommending the cultivation of rice in UP fields, because brown spot may become a limiting factor. ■

Integrated pest management—diseases

Effect of submergence of rice plants on the development of sheath blight

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During the monsoon season, heavy and continuous rainfall keeps plants under water for extended periods of time. We studied the impact of submergence on sheath blight (ShB) infection in rice.

Plants of a highly susceptible rice cultivar, Annapurna, were grown in pots well supplied with fertilizer. When the plants were at flowering stage, leaf sheaths of the second youngest leaves in each of three tillers per plant were inoculated with a sterilized rice "stem" piece colonized by the causal fungus, *Rhizoctonia solani* Kühn.

Three days after inoculation, grayish-green lesions measuring 3.0-3.5 cm developed on the inoculated tillers. The inoculum was gently removed with sterilized forceps, and the plants were submerged to establish lesions. The plants were removed from water at intervals and placed in a glasshouse. Three replications were maintained for each treatment. On the 14th d after inoculation, lesions on each inoculated tiller was measured at the same time with leaf infection and sclerotia produced.

Results indicated that submergence of the infected plants greatly reduced the development of ShB (see table). Disease continued to develop in plants that were under water for 2 d, but beyond that period we observed a sudden and strong decrease in the progress of infection. Disease develop-

Development of ShB infection in rice plants subjected to submergence, Cuttack, India, 1996 WS.

Duration of submergence (d)	Mean lesion length (cm)	Extent of leaf infection ^a	Sclerotia produced (no.)
0	38.7	++	18
2	28.2	++	5
4	12.3	+	3
6	6.7	-	0
8	4.0	-	0
10	3.7	-	0
Continuous submergence	No further infection		
Control (no submergence)	45.5	+++	26
CD for treatments			
5% = 5.1			
1% = 7.1			

^a- = none, + = slight, ++ = moderate, +++ = severe.

ment in 6, 8, and 10-d submergence treatments was significantly lower than in 0, 2, and 4-d treatments. Almost no

disease developed in the continuous submergence treatment. Control treatments, in which the plants were not subjected to submergence, showed significantly highest disease with higher leaf infection and more sclerotia than all other treatments.

Prolonged submergence is not a favorable environment for rapid mycelia proliferation and infection in the host. ■

Effect of crop growth stage and N level on leaf blast monocyclic parameters on a new rice plant type

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We studied the effect of crop growth stage and applied N on leaf blast monocyclic parameters in two blast-susceptible cultivars, a new rice plant type line, IR64454-81-1-3-2, and with IR72 serving as the control (see table). Sporulation was converted to area under the sporulation curve (AUSC, in spores lesion⁻¹ d⁻¹) using the equation

$$AUSC = \sum_{i=1}^n [(X_{i+1} + X_i)/2] \cdot [t_{i+1} - t_i]$$

where X_i = number of spores produced at i th observation, T_i = time (d) between observations, and n = total number of observations.

The first greenhouse experiment used a split-split plot randomized complete block design with three replications. Three pregerminated seeds were directly sown in each plastic pot (500 cm³) of 0.5 kg soil, and the plants thinned to one plant at 7 d after sowing. Urea N (46-0-0) was applied in three equal splits. Inoculum (20 mL of *Pyricularia grisea* isolate PO6-6) at 150,000 spores mL⁻¹ was sprayed at a height of 1.5 m inside a 0.8 × 0.8 × 1.5-m chamber on 12 plants using an atomizer at 10 psi for 30 s. Plants were inside dew chambers for 24 h in a mist room for 5 d.

The second experiment used the same procedure, but 50 mL of inoculum was sprayed on six plants per sub-subplot inside a 3.5 × 3.5 × 1-m chamber placed in an air-conditioned room and leaves were sprayed with water hourly in daytime and covered with wet jute sacks and polyethylene sheets at night. At 12 h after inoculation, 1 cm leaf portions were cut from the top, middle, and bottom of three plants, fixed in 50% glycerin, and the number of spores counted. Leaf area was measured per plant using a Licor LI-3000 leaf area meter. Incubation period was determined by counting the lesions per plant daily starting from inoculation up to 7 d inside the mist room. Sporulation was assessed on five isolated lesions on the two upper leaves of three sample plants every morning up to 5 d of symptoms using small agar disks of known area. The number of spores produced per lesion was counted on three isolated sporulating lesions located on the two upper leaves of three sample plants at 3-d intervals starting 5 d after inoculation.

Crop growth stage affected leaf blast lesion area, severity, infection ratio, latent period, and AUSC (see table). Cultivar type affected all monocyclic parameters, except for the latent

period. Other authors have reported nonsignificant differences in latent period among cultivars with susceptible lesion types. Nitrogen level affected lesion area, infection ratio, and AUSC. Lesion area at maximum tillering stage was significantly higher than the lesion areas at early tillering and early booting stages. Leaf blast severity and infection ratio at early tillering stage was significantly higher than the leaf blast severity at early booting stage. Latent periods at early and maximum tillering stages were significantly lower than the latent period at early booting stage. The highest AUSC was observed at early tillering stage and decreased as crop growth stage progressed (see table). Leaf blast lesion area, severity, infection ratio, incubation period, and AUSC were higher on IR72 than on the new plant type (see table). Lesion area significantly increased as N level increased from 0 to 180 kg N ha⁻¹. The effect of N level on leaf blast severity was not significant. Infection ratios at 90 and 180 kg N ha⁻¹ were significantly higher than the infection ratio at 0 kg N ha⁻¹ but not between each other. A significantly higher AUSC was observed at 180 kg N ha⁻¹ than at 0 and 90 kg N ha⁻¹. ■

Effects of crop growth stage, cultivar, and N level on leaf blast monocyclic parameters.^a

Treatment	Lesion area ^b (cm ² plant ⁻¹)	Severity ^{b,d} (% plant ⁻¹)	Infection ratio ^b plant ⁻¹ /no. (no. lesions spores deposited plant ⁻¹)	Incubation period ^b (d)	Latent period ^b (d)	AUSC ^{c,e} (no. spores lesion ⁻¹ d ⁻¹)
Main plot (crop growth stage)						
Early tillering (15 DAS)	0.357 b	0.99 a	0.01248 a	6 a	6 a	2637 a
Maximum tillering (30 DAS)	1.036 a	0.27 ab	0.00392 ab	5 a	6 a	723 b
Early booting (45 DAS)	0.049 b	0.01 b	0.00022 b	6 a	7 b	109 c
Subplot (cultivar)						
IR72	0.772 a	0.54 a	0.00924 a	6 a	6 a	1440 a
New plant type	0.189 b	0.32 b	0.00184 b	5 b	6 a	873 b
Sub-subplot (N level)						
0 kg N ha ⁻¹	0.131 a	0.37 a	0.00368 a	5 a	6 a	718 a
90 kg N ha ⁻¹	0.442 b	0.44 a	0.00681 b	6 a	6 a	976 a
180 kg N ha ⁻¹	0.868 c	0.47 a	0.00612 b	6 a	6 a	1775 b

^aIn each factor within a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different by LSD at 5% level. ^bIncubation period = no. of days from inoculation until 50% of final no. of lesion is reached. Severity (%) = lesion area divided by the leaf area multiplied by 100. Latent period = no. of days from inoculation until 50% of the lesions start sporulating. Means of two trials with three replications. ^cMeans of three replications. ^dSeverity at 1 wk after inoculation. ^eAUSC = area under the sporulation curve.